

TACTICAL TERRAIN DATA - SPATIAL DATA FOR THE 1990's

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ABSTRACT

In 1984, the Army completed a comprehensive study of the known and anticipated digital terrain requirements of approximately 75 systems/applications. The Defense Mapping Agency (DMA) recognized this digital topographic data requirement in 1985 and indicated that production against this requirement could begin in the early 1990's, once their MK90 Production System was in place. Since its recognition as an Army requirement, Tactical Terrain Data (TTD) has evolved into a joint service resource with unparalleled potential for support of land combat operations. TTD, currently in prototype form, contains Digital Terrain Elevation Data (DTED) at one arc second resolution as well as feature information equivalent to an enhanced 1:50,000 scale Tactical Terrain Analysis Data Base. It also contains selected features from the 1:50,000 scale Topographic Line Map and Combat Chart.

BACKGROUND

Definition of the Army's requirement for digital topographic data did not occur overnight, but rather, has been an evolutionary, iterative process beginning in earnest in 1980. In October of that year, the Army requested that the DMA produce a prototype data set to assist in defining the content, format, accuracy, and resolution requirements of a future digital topographic data base. In 1982, following DMA's completion of a prototype for areas in Fort Lewis and Yakima Firing Center, Washington, the Army initiated a comprehensive study that lasted two years. During the first phase of this study, Army evaluators studied the content, format, accuracy, and resolution of these prototype data sets and tested their adequacy for terrain analysis support. The study's second phase examined the data sets in terms of terrain data requirements which will be generated by existing and planned tactical and training systems. As part of this effort, over 75 Army activities were contacted.

In October 1984, following completion of this comprehensive study, the Army stated its requirement for digital topographic data to DMA. This stated requirement defined a multi-use data set capable of supporting a broad range of land combat functions and systems in the 1990's and beyond. In October 1985, DMA recognized this digital topographic data requirement and indicated that production against this requirement could begin in the early 1990's, once their MK-90 Production System was in place.

JOINT PARTICIPATION

Since its recognition as an Army requirement, TTD, as it is now called, has been the subject of negotiations between DMA, Army, Navy, Marine Corps, and Air Force representatives. In July 1986, DMA organized a Joint DOD TTD Working Group to serve as a forum to further refine the overall design and characteristics of TTD to better support the multiplicity of intended uses by joint land combat forces in the future. To this end, selected 1:50,000 scale Combat Chart information on near shore hydrographic features have been added to the data set for intended Marine Corps' uses. This is in addition to the remainder of the data set that includes an enhanced Tactical Terrain Analysis Data Base, selected features from the 1:50,000 scale Topographic Line Map, and a DTED Level II elevation matrix. The content of TTD is shown graphically in Figure 1.

PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT

In order to provide the services with "hands-on" knowledge of TTD, DMA produced a prototype 15' x 15' cell over Fort Hood, TX. This cell is DMA's "best shot" at providing a data set that simulates their production capabilities of the 1990's. A synopsis of TTD characteristics, to include information on content, accuracy, applications, storage

TACTICAL TERRAIN DATA (TTD) CONTENT

Figure 1. Tactical Terrain Data Content Diagram

requirements, etc., is provided in Table 1.

The original date for delivery of a spatially integrated (single spatial layer) prototype was 31 Dec 87. An initial delivery of the prototype did occur in February 1988, however, this version contained separate thematic layers. Unforeseen difficulties in achieving a fully integrated 15' x 15' cell prevented timely delivery of this target prototype. Due to these difficulties, DMA's contractor divided the 15' x 15' area into nine 5' x 5' subcells (tiles) and iteratively integrated them one tile at a time. The first of these 5' x 5' integrated tiles was delivered in mid summer.

PROTOTYPE EVALUATION

In order to expedite initiation of the evaluation, the nonintegrated version of the prototype was distributed first to the military services. The U.S. Army Engineer Topographic Laboratories (USAETL), as the lead agency responsible for evaluation of the TTD prototype, developed a schedule for prototype evaluation and for reporting results back to DMA. In order to ensure both a complete and a timely evaluation of the prototype, a two phased evaluation was planned. Phase I, originally scheduled to begin in Mar 88, was re-scheduled to run from approximately 1 Sept through 31 Dec 88. This schedule slippage was directly attributable to delay in delivery of the prototype. Due to this compression of time available for Phase I, evaluation results will be weighted towards a content evaluation which can be

Table 1. Tactical Terrain Data Characteristics

Prototype
Tactical Terrain Data (TTD)

1. PRODUCT SPECIFICATION: To be provided with prototype.
2. DENSITY: Elevation data will be a one arc-second spacing (nominally 30 meters); feature density varies with actual density of depicted features (normally equivalent to that portrayed at 1:50,000 scale on line maps or factor overlays).
3. COORDINATE REFERENCE SYSTEM: Geographic.
4. DATUM: Horizontal - World Geodetic System (WGS)
Vertical - Mean Sea Level (MSL)
5. CONTENT: TTD contains both elevation and feature data. The elevation data consist of DTED Level II. The feature data are in a topologically integrated file containing data consistent with the Tactical Terrain Analysis Data Base (TTADB) thematic overlays and special features from the 1:50,000 Topographic Line Map (TLM) and combat chart as follows:

<u>Themes</u>	<u>Content Examples</u>
Surface Configuration	Slope expressed in percentage ranges
Surface Materials	Soil types
Vegetation	Type, height, canopy closure
Transportation	Roads, bridges, tunnels
Surface Drainage	Gap widths, bank slopes/heights
Obstacles	Natural and/or man-made features that divert movement
Urban Areas	Predominant use/heights
Special Features from 1:50,000 topographic line maps and combat charts	Reefs, wells, gas/oil storage facilities

Note: User-defined Geographic Information System must have the capability to extract these user themes from the integrated file.

6. STRUCTURE: Elevation data - matrix; Feature data - Minimally Redundant Topology (MINITOP). Feature categories will be those contained in the Feature Attribute Coding Standard (FACS).
7. FORMAT: Spatial Data Transfer Specification (SDTS) is the exchange format for the initial TTD prototype. SDTS incorporates American National Standards Institutes (ANSI) ISO-8211 at the transport level.
8. MEDIA: Initially 9 track, 6250 BPI magnetic tape; future prototypes may be CD-ROM optical disk; production TTD to be on suitable high density, durable media (such as optical digital disk).
9. STANDARD FILE SIZE: 15 minute by 15 minute cell.
10. ACCURACY: Accuracy of elevation and feature information will be consistent with the most current class 2,1:50,000 Topographic Line Map Specification.
11. AREA COVERAGE: To be identified by customers in the 1988 area requirements process; first prototype to cover one 15' X 15' area (approximately 22 km X 27 km) of Fort Hood, TX.
12. APPLICATIONS: TTD, as the basic operational terrain data set for future land combat, will provide terrain information that is critical to planning and executing joint operations including close air support missions, amphibious operations, and land combat operations. These data will support such diverse tasks as terrain visualization, mobility/counter mobility planning, site/route selection, reconnaissance planning, fire planning, communication planning, navigation, and munition guidance.
13. DISTRIBUTION POLICY: Distribution of these data will be limited to agencies within the Executive Branch of the U.S. Government and qualified DoD contractors.
14. STORAGE REQUIREMENTS: Initial TTD prototype is approximately 20 MB. Production TTD storage requirements will vary depending upon the density of depicted features.
15. CLASSIFICATION: Initial prototype will be unclassified. Future prototypes and/or production TTD may be classified.
16. POINTS OF CONTACT: DAMI-ISP MAJ Jens (202) 695-5509, AUTOVON 225-5509; HQ DMASC(SGW) LTC Smith (703) 285-5922, AUTOVON 294-5922.

Figure 2. Masked Area Plot

Intervisibility products, in general, provide predictions of visible or electronic line-of-sight over a user specified area. The primary input utilized by these models is digital terrain elevation data. Mobility products, on the other hand, provide predictions related to a units' ability to move over the ground surface. These models are input data intensive and require detailed information on land cover conditions.

Figure 2 provides an example of a graphic output from the masked area plot model, an intervisibility product. This model displays areas around a site or a number of sites in which a target, at a user specified altitude, is shielded from an observer. As a target approaches an observer site, the target may be visible to the observer then dip into masked zones at various points along its path. The masked area plot displays these areas of target shielding due to intervening

performed as a paper study. All evaluators will be encouraged to participate in this phase of the evaluation to the extent that they are able as this will be the best opportunity to influence design of MK-90 production TTD. Phase II of the evaluation will run concurrently with Phase I, its purpose is to accommodate those users that cannot meet the 31 Dec 88 completion date. Currently, Phase II has no firm completion date.

POTENTIAL FOR THE FUTURE

The potential for this dataset to support land combat operations is limited only by the imagination of its user. The Army in particular is committed to the use of TTD as its primary source of terrain information. Though the

evaluation of the prototype has yet to be completed, it is believed that the vast majority of Army users will be fully satisfied by its content, accuracy, and resolution. A number of applications have already been developed and demonstrated and a myriad of others are sure to follow. For example, USAETL is currently developing a system called the Digital Topographic Support System (DTSS) which will employ TTD. This system is in full scale development with Initial Operational Capability (IOC) in 1992 and will be deployed at Corps and Division level.

DTSS will have the capability to produce a number of terrain products in support of the field commander. Table 2 lists these products under the main headings of Intervisibility and Mobility.

Table 2. Application Products	
<u>Intervisibility</u>	
	Terrain Profile Plot
	Masked Area Plot
	Target Acquisition Plot
	Multiple Site Target Acquisition Plot
	Perspective Plot
	Oblique Projection Plot
	Flight Line Masking Plot
	Path Loss/Line-of-Sight Plot
<u>Mobility</u>	
	Cross Country Movement Map
	Concealment Map
	River Crossing Graphic
	Air Avenues of Approach Graphic
	Drop Zone Graphic
	Helicopter Landing Zone Graphic
	Local Relief Display
	Key Terrain Plot

Figure 3. Cross Country Movement Map

terrain conditions. Figure 3 illustrates a graphic output from the cross country movement model, a mobility product. This model predicts the ability of a user-specified friendly or threat vehicle to move off-road based on the terrain conditions in a given operational area. This prediction is made on the basis of vehicle parameters and the terrain characteristics of slope, soil, and vegetation. The output is then coded in terms of user-defined speed categories or the more general predictions of "GO", "SLO-GO", and "NO-GO".

SUMMARY

The military services are currently working closely with DMA to define a multiuse dataset with unparalleled potential for support of land combat operations. Following evaluation of the TTD prototype, and the analysis of these results by DMA, the services look forward to the mid 1990's when this data set will be a standard output from DMA's modernized production system.